

Different kinds of regression

Harald Schröer

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We know the linear regression. Because of this, the linear regression is not treated here. The linear regression is used at Schröer [2].

Now we view the logarithmic regression. The relation is expressed as $y = a + b \cdot \ln x$. One example is the following table over the age and the mass of newborns:

age in days	mass in gram
20	3150
50	4800
80	6420
110	7310
140	7940
170	8690
200	8800
230	9130
260	9270
290	9310
320	9390

We use the following formulas:

$$a = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n y_i - b \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n}$$

$$b = \frac{n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (\ln x_i) y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (\ln x_i)^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i)^2}$$

with the correlation coefficient

$$r = \frac{n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (\ln x_i) y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{\sqrt{\left(n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (\ln x_i)^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i)^2 \right) \cdot \left(n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n y_i)^2 \right)}}$$

The calculations lead to $a=-1209.35654$, $b=2425.75623$ and $r=0.99149312$. Thus we have the relation:

$$y = -4209.35654 + 2425.75623 \cdot \ln x$$

We turn to the exponential regression $y = a \cdot e^{bx}$. An example is the transmission of light through a liquid or glass. We look at the following table. x is the covered distance in metres, y the intensity of transmitted light (irradiance) and $-b$ is the absorption coefficient:

x_i	y_i
1	0.50
2	0.06
3	0.01
4	0.001
5	0.0002
6	0.00002
7	$8 \cdot 10^{-7}$
8	$5 \cdot 10^{-7}$
9	$6 \cdot 10^{-8}$
10	$8 \cdot 10^{-9}$

For the calculation we need the following terms:

$$a = \exp \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \ln y_i - \ln b \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n} \right)$$

with

$$b = \frac{n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \ln y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n \ln y_i}{n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i)^2}$$

The correlation coefficient can be written:

$$r = \frac{n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \ln y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n \ln y_i}{\sqrt{\left(n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i)^2 \right) \cdot \left(n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (\ln y_i)^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n \ln y_i)^2 \right)}}$$

The calculation leads to $a=3.42717752$, $b=-2.00894095$ and $|r|=0.99730837$. We get the following relation:

$$y = 3.42717752 \cdot e^{-2.00894095 \cdot x}$$

Now we deal with another kind of exponential regression $y = a \cdot b^x$. For example light is going through plates with transmission factor $b < 1$. We take the following table with the number of plates= x and the transmitted intensity= y :

x_i	y_i
1	0.5
2	0.06
3	0.01
4	0.001
5	0.0002
6	0.00002
7	$7 \cdot 10^{-7}$
8	$4 \cdot 10^{-7}$
9	$5 \cdot 10^{-8}$
10	$8 \cdot 10^{-9}$

For calculation of r we need the same formula as at the exponential regression of the first kind. a and b change to:

$$a = \exp \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \ln y_i - \ln b \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n} \right)$$

$$b = \exp \left(\frac{n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \ln y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n \ln y_i}{n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i)^2} \right)$$

We get $a=3.56363394$, $|r|=0.99713700$ and $b=0.13187794$. Thus we have the relation:

$$y = 3.56363394 \cdot 0.13187794^x$$

Now we treat the power regression $y = a \cdot x^b$. An example is with y the mass of newborns and with x the mass of the mother. We view the following table:

x_i [kg]	y_i [kg]
45	1.7
50	2.0
60	3.0
70	4.0
80	5.0
90	5.5
100	6.0
110	6.5

We use the following formulas

$$a = \exp \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \ln y_i - b \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i}{n} \right)$$

with

$$b = \frac{n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (\ln x_i \cdot \ln y_i) - \sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n \ln y_i}{n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (\ln x_i)^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i)^2}$$

and

$$r = \frac{n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (\ln x_i \cdot \ln y_i) - \sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n \ln y_i}{\sqrt{\left(n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (\ln x_i)^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i)^2\right) \cdot \left(n \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (\ln y_i)^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n \ln y_i)^2\right)}}$$

The calculation yields $a = 0.00494454520$, $b = 1.55222556$ and $r = 0.98550073$. We get the following relation:

$$y = 0.00494454520 \cdot x^{1.55222556}$$

Now we occupy with the quadratic regression $y = ax^2 + bx + c$. An example is the covered distance as y in metres and the belonging time as x in seconds with following table:

x_i	y_i
1	5
2	20
3	44
4	79
5	120
6	178

We need the following formulas:

$$a = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{n} - b \cdot \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n} - c \cdot \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2}{n}$$

with

$$b = \frac{S_{xy} \cdot S_{x^2x^2} - S_{x^2y} \cdot S_{xx^2}}{S_{xx} \cdot S_{x^2x^2} - (S_{xx^2})^2}$$

and

$$c = \frac{S_{x^2y} \cdot S_{xx} - S_{xy} \cdot S_{xx^2}}{S_{xx} \cdot S_{x^2x^2} - (S_{xx^2})^2}$$

it is:

$$S_{xx} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i)^2}{n}$$

$$S_{xy} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i - \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n y_i)}{n}$$

$$S_{xx^2} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^3 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2}{n}$$

$$S_{x^2x^2} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^4 - \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2)^2}{n}$$

$$S_{x^2y} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 y_i - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{n}$$

The calculations lead to $c=1.5$, $b = -1.08928571$ and $a = 5.05357143$. We get the following relation:

$$y = f(x) = 1.5 - 1.08928571 \cdot x + 5.05357143 \cdot x^2$$

For the correlation coefficient r it is valid:

$$r = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (f(x_i) - \bar{y})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

with $\bar{y} = \frac{1}{n} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n y_i$. We obtain $r = 0.9980344$.

At last we turn to the inverse regression $y = a + \frac{b}{x}$. An example is with x as used time (in months) and y as measure of the solidity:

x_i	y_i
1	7
2	6
3	5.8
4	5.5
5	5.4
6	5.3
7	5.25
8	5.2
9	5.15
10	5.1

We use the following equations:

$$a = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n y_i - b \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^{-1}}{n} \quad \text{with} \quad b = \frac{S_{xy}}{S_{xx}}$$

it is:

$$S_{xx} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^{-2} - \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^{-1})^2}{n}$$

and

$$S_{xy} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^{-1} y_i - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^{-1} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{n}$$

The correlation coefficient can be written:

$$r = \frac{S_{xy}}{\sqrt{S_{xx} \cdot S_{yy}}}$$

with

$$S_{i,y} = \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2 - \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n y_i)^2}{n}$$

The calculation yields $a=4.96059652$, $b= 2.08960802$ and $r= 0.99488274$. We get the following relation:

$$y = 4.96059652 + \frac{2.08960802}{x}$$

Further application of inverse regression are in geophysics.

References

- [1] Bronstein, Semendjajew " Taschenbuch der Mathematik" 22.edition 1985 Teubner Verlag Leipsic
- [2] Harald Schröder "Adaptation with series of measurements" Planet Poster Editions 2003